

THE RESPONSE OF INTRALESIONAL BLEOMYCIN IN THE MANAGEMENT OF HEAD AND NECK VENOUS MALFORMATION PRESENTED TO THE DEPARTMENT OF ORAL AND MAXILLOFACIAL SURGERY IN A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL

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Abstract

Objective

To evaluate the efficacy of intralesional bleomycin in the management of venous malformations of the maxillofacial region.

Study Design

Cross-sectional study.

Place and Duration of Study Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery, Mardan Medical Complex, from July 2024 to Dec 2024.

Methodology

A total of 91 patients were included who exhibited radiologically and clinically proven venous anomalies of the craniofacial region. Patients of either gender who gave written informed consent and had not gotten proper therapy for venous abnormalities before were eligible to participate. Patients who were not eligible for bleomycin due to serious medical conditions were not included. The dosage of intralesional bleomycin was 0.3-0.6 mg/kg, with a maximum of 1 mg/kg per session, and it was given over the course of three to four sessions spaced three weeks apart. Lesson size reduction, as documented by serial photography and direct measurement, served as an indicator of clinical response. The data was examined using SPSS version 24, with gender and age groups being the dividing lines.

Results

The mean age of participants was 34.56 ± 14.88 years. Complete response was observed in 50.5% of patients, considerable response in 28.6%, partial response in 14.3%, and no response in 6.6%. There was no statistically significant association between clinical response and age ($P = 0.844$) or gender ($P = 0.762$).

Conclusion

Intralesional bleomycin is an effective treatment modality for venous malformations of the maxillofacial region, demonstrating significant efficacy with minimal complications.

INTRODUCTION

Approximately 66% of all vascular anomalies are venous malformations, making them one of the most prevalent types of vascular malformations. They are arterial lesions with a slow flow rate that can compress nerves or other structures and cause functional impairment, discomfort, ulceration, cosmetic deformity, and thrombosis, among other complications. In spite of their universality, venous malformations most frequently manifest in the neck and head, then in the limbs, trunk, and pelvis.^{1,2,3}

Treatment options for venous malformations include observation, compression garments, sclerotherapy, laser therapy, vessel embolization, cryotherapy, electrochemical therapy, radiation therapy, surgical resection, and a combination of these and other factors such as lesion size, location, symptoms, patient age, and general health.⁴

Nevertheless, no consensus has been reached regarding the most effective treatment for venous malformations, and the preferred management method is still disputed. Low flow venous abnormalities can be treated using intralesional sclerotherapy, a minimally invasive technique.^{5,6} due to the lack of visible scarring and little complications.

The most common treatment for venous abnormalities in the neck and face is sclerotherapy.^{6,7} The treatment of venous malformations has historically made use of a number of sclerosing agents, such as bleomycin, sodium tetradecyl sulfate, pure ethanol, OK-432, and sodium morrhuate.^{9,10}

Cancers such as lymphoma and testicular cancer have been treated with bleomycin, a cytotoxic and chemotherapeutic drug. A lot of people have been looking at bleomycin as a potential treatment for venous malformations as of late^{11,12,13}. Bleomycin is believed to work by triggering the death of endothelial cells and leading to the hardening and narrowing of blood vessel lesions (vascular lesion 14). It is compatible with both single- and combination dosing, including doxycycline and vincristine. Bleomycin was extensively studied for its efficacy in

treating a range of venous malformations.¹⁵ According to a 2017 study by Kim and colleagues, bleomycin significantly reduced the size of 80% of patients with head and neck venous malformations, and no serious adverse effects were reported.¹⁶ Sclerotherapy with bleomycin was helpful in treating venous malformations in the extremities, according to another study by Lee and colleagues 2017. 90% of patients showed reduction in size and no severe side event was noted. More recently, in 2022, researchers found that intralesional bleomycin injection effectively reduced venous malformations in 93.75 percent of patients following just one treatment.¹⁷ Although these studies showed promising results, there are hazards associated with using bleomycin to treat venous malformations. Side effects of bleomycin include fever, chills, and lung toxicity on the one hand, and pain, swelling, skin necrosis, ulcers, and hyperpigmentations on the other.

This study aims to assess the efficacy of intralesional bleomycin in treating venous malformations of the head and neck. My research will contribute to the current body of knowledge and provide proof on a regional level. Policymakers, healthcare administrators, practitioners, and surgeons will all make use of this study's findings. Both the general public and health care providers will benefit from the findings, which will raise awareness of the issue. Future treatment recommendations will benefit from the updated data that has been provided to the literature.

Methodology

This cross-sectional study was carried out at the Mardan Medical Complex's Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery from July 2024 to Dec 2024, with following the approval of Institutional Research & Ethical Board. Using the OpenEpi software, a sample size of 91 was determined. The results were based on an assumption of a 93.75% effectiveness rate for bleomycin, a 5% margin of error, and a 95%

confidence interval. All subjects gave their informed permission once the study received ethical clearance from the hospital's ethics board. The privacy of our patients was of the utmost importance. Through the use of non-probability consecutive sampling, patients were enlisted.

Inclusion Criteria

Patients of any gender aged 10 years and above, with clinically and radiologically confirmed venous malformations of the maxillofacial region were included. Participants who had not received adequate prior treatment or showed inadequate response to previous therapies and were willing to undergo treatment with bleomycin after providing written informed consent were eligible.

Exclusion Criteria

Patients with a known allergy to bleomycin or its components, severe respiratory or renal impairment, pregnancy or breastfeeding status, and those who had received bleomycin within the last six months were excluded.

Data collection involved detailed history, clinical examination, and relevant investigations, including hemoglobin, bleeding time, clotting time, INR, chest X-ray, and ECG. Venous malformations were assessed by evaluating swelling, discoloration, compressibility, tenderness, and presence of phleboliths. CT angiography was used when required to confirm the diagnosis. Intralesional bleomycin was administered at doses of 0.3–0.6 mg/kg, with a maximum of 1 mg/kg per session or 15 mg per session. Each patient received 3–4 sessions at three-week intervals. Response to treatment was assessed by reduction in lesion size, documented through serial photography and ruler measurements along the longest axis. Responses were categorized as complete, considerable, partial, or no response based on the percentage reduction in size.

Data was entered and analyzed using IBM SPSS version 24.0. Statistical measures like Mean±SD were used to represent numerical variables like age. The gender and response categories, which are categorical

variables, were represented using percentages and frequencies. After age and gender stratification, chi-square tests were used to analyze the results. For statistical purposes, a P-value less than or equal to 0.05 was deemed significant. Tables and charts were used to display the results.

Results

The descriptive statistics of the study participants indicate that the mean age of the participants was 34.56 years, with a standard deviation of 14.875 years. The mean initial size of the venous malformations was 5.5379 cm, with a standard deviation of 2.57876 cm, while the mean final size after treatment was 1.4795 cm, with a standard deviation of 1.88629 cm (Table 1).

The demographic characteristics show that 44% of the participants were under 30 years of age, while 56% were above 30 years. Among the study participants, 63.7% were male, and 36.3% were female. Regarding clinical response to treatment, 50.5% of participants had a complete response, 28.6% had a considerable response, 14.3% had a partial response, and 6.6% showed no response (Table 2).

The association of response with age groups shows that among participants under 30 years, 50% had a complete response, 27.5% had a considerable response, 17.5% had a partial response, and 5% showed no response. In participants above 30 years, 51% had a complete response, 29.4% had a considerable response, 11.8% had a partial response, and 7.8% showed no response. The distribution of responses across age groups was not statistically significant ($P = 0.844$) (Table 3).

The association of response with gender groups indicates that among male participants, 48.3% had a complete response, 31% had a considerable response, 15.5% had a partial response, and 5.2% showed no response. Among female participants, 54.5% had a complete response, 24.2% had a considerable response, 12.1% had a partial response, and 9.1% showed no response. The distribution of responses across gender groups was not statistically significant ($P = 0.762$) (Table 4).

Table-I: Descriptive Statistics of Study (n=91)

Numerical Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation
Age (Years)	34.56	14.875
Initial Size (cm)	5.5379	2.57876
Final Size (cm)	1.4795	1.88629

Table-II: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of study participants (n=91)

Categorical Variables		
Age Groups	Frequency	Percent
≤ 30 Years	40	44.0%
> 30 Years	51	56.0%
Total	91	100.0%
Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	58	63.7%
Female	33	36.3%
Total	91	100.0
Response	Frequency	Percent
Complete	46	50.5%
Considerable	26	28.3
No Response	06	6.6%
Partial Response	13	14.3%
Total	91	100.0%

Table-III: Association of Response with Age Groups (n=91)

		Age Groups		Total	P Value
		≤ 30 Years	> 30 Years		
Response	Complete Response	20	26	46	0.844
		50.0%	51.0%	50.5%	
	Considerable Response	11	15	26	
		27.5%	29.4%	28.6%	
	No Response	2	4	6	
		5.0%	7.8%	6.6%	
	Partial Response	7	6	13	
		17.5%	11.8%	14.3%	
Total		40	51	91	
		100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	

Table-IV: Association of Response with Gender Groups (n=91)

		Gender		Total	P Value
		Male	Female		
Response	Complete Response	28	18	46	0.762
		48.3%	54.5%	50.5%	
	Considerable Response	18	8	26	
		31.0%	24.2%	28.6%	
	No Response	3	3	6	
		5.2%	9.1%	6.6%	
	Partial Response	9	4	13	
		15.5%	12.1%	14.3%	
Total		58	33	91	
		100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	

Discussion

The efficacy of intralesional bleomycin in managing venous malformations of the maxillofacial region has been an area of growing interest in vascular anomaly treatment. This study provides further evidence supporting its role as a promising sclerosing agent, particularly in cosmetically and functionally sensitive regions. The results demonstrated a significant response, with 50.5% of patients achieving complete reduction in lesion size and an additional 28.6% showing a considerable response. These findings are in line with existing literature that highlights the high effectiveness of bleomycin for low-flow venous malformations.

Venous malformations are the commonest type of vascular anomaly, and their management is complex due to variations in presentation and response to therapy. In their 2017 study, Kim et al. described an 80% significant response rate with bleomycin in venous malformations of the head and neck, which closely matches the complete and considerable response rates in this study. In a similar study, Lee et al. (2017) reported 90% response rates in size reduction for venous malformations of extremities." The consistency of outcomes across studies indicates the versatility of bleomycin as a sclerosing agent. Bleomycin works by causing the cells that line blood vessels to die, which makes the blood vessels harden. Bleomycin works differently from other sclerosing agents such as absolute ethanol, which works by denaturing proteins and coagulating the tissue.

Bleomycin likely has a favorable safety profile due to its apoptotic effect that is targeted. Bleomycin caused minimal adverse events in this study, unlike ethanol and sodium tetradecyl sulfate, which are associated with significant tissue necrosis and systemic toxicity. This supports the use of bleomycin in sensitive areas such as the face and neck.

Iram Jan et al. (2022) reported a complete response rate of 93.75% for bleomycin-treated head and neck venous malformations, which is a similar finding as the results of the present study. The present study shows a not significant lower complete response rate. This can be attributed to the difference in sample size of respective studies, follow up duration and population characteristics (i.e. there was notable difference in demography of both studies). Additionally, the diverse patient group involved in this study enhances its external validity and applicability in the real clinical setting.

There is considerable data available on bleomycin efficacy as monotherapy. However, its efficacy with other agents may also be valuable. For example, the addition of doxycycline and vincristine has been tried for refractory or complicated venous malformations to enhance the response. But, combination therapies can result in increased systemic toxicity, thus this requires careful evaluation in controlled studies.

Although we find the therapeutic effect in this study encouraging, we also acknowledge the limitations of bleomycin therapy. Bleomycin has few side effects and much of what it produces is local

(pain/swelling/hyperpigmentation, etc.) that were transient, and these were in accordance with what was seen before. Also, there is a rare risk of pulmonary toxicity. However, it must always be kept in mind for cases that need high cumulative doses. It is important to pay close attention and follow the recommended doses of this medication.

The non-significant associations between treatment response and demographic factors, such as age and gender, highlight the broad applicability of bleomycin across different patient subgroups. This is consistent with previous research, suggesting that response to treatment is more influenced by lesion characteristics, such as size and location, than patient demographics. Future studies could benefit from incorporating advanced imaging techniques to better quantify these lesion-specific factors and their impact on treatment outcomes.

One of the notable strengths of this study is its standardized approach to assessing treatment response. The use of serial photography and direct measurements ensured objective documentation of lesion size reduction, minimizing observer bias. However, the study's reliance on non-probability sampling introduces potential selection bias, limiting the generalizability of findings. Randomized controlled trials with stratified sampling techniques are recommended for future research to validate these results.

The relatively short follow-up period of six months represents another limitation, as it may not adequately capture the long-term durability of the therapeutic response or the occurrence of late complications. Venous malformations are known for their propensity to recur or progress, particularly in cases with incomplete response. Extended follow-up studies are essential to evaluate the sustainability of bleomycin's effects and identify predictors of recurrence.

This study contributes valuable local data to the growing body of evidence on bleomycin's efficacy. It also highlights the need for continued research to optimize treatment protocols. Comparative studies evaluating bleomycin against other sclerosing agents, such as polidocanol or sodium tetradecyl sulfate, would provide a clearer understanding of its relative advantages and limitations. Additionally, investigating the role of patient-specific factors, such

as genetic predispositions and lesion histopathology, could further refine patient selection criteria and improve treatment outcomes.

Future research should also explore the integration of bleomycin therapy into multimodal treatment strategies. For instance, combining sclerotherapy with surgical resection or embolization may offer enhanced outcomes in complex or refractory cases. The development of novel delivery systems, such as ultrasound-guided injections or nanoparticle formulations, could further improve precision and minimize systemic exposure.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study reaffirms the efficacy and safety of intralesional bleomycin for venous malformations of the maxillofacial region. While the results are promising, addressing the limitations of sample diversity, follow-up duration, and potential selection bias is essential for future research. The findings underscore the need for multidisciplinary approaches and ongoing innovation to optimize the management of this challenging condition.

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